

Open Science

Concepts and practices

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Departmental Science Seminar Series of at the NNF Center for Biosustainability (DTU, Denmark)

2023-01-31

(Logos and websites of others excluded)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7588461>

https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/9/97/The_Earth_seen_from_Apollo_17.jpg

Cost per Genome

A close-up photograph of two cats huddled together on a grey, textured blanket. The cats have brown and white fur. One cat is in the foreground, and the other is slightly behind it. A semi-transparent white rectangular box is overlaid in the center of the image, containing the text "Open & FAIR".

Open & FAIR

Key message:

Openness, transparency, reproducibility are core values of science.

OPEN SCIENCE

Open Science is a system change allowing for better science through open and collaborative ways of producing and sharing knowledge and data, as early as possible in the research process, and for communicating and sharing results. This new approach affects research institutions and science practices by bringing about new ways of funding, evaluating and rewarding researchers. Open Science increases the quality and impact of science by fostering reproducibility and interdisciplinarity. It makes science more efficient through better sharing of resources, more reliable through better verification and more responsive to society's needs.

The eight ambitions of Open Science

Open science policy has developed progressively in the EU. It concerns all aspects of the research cycle, from scientific discovery and scientific review to research assessment, publishing and outreach; its cornerstone being open access to publications and research data. Since 2016, the Commission organises its open science policy according to eight 'ambitions':

- Open Data: FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable data) and open data sharing should become the default for the results of EU-funded scientific research.
- European Open Science Cloud (EOSC): a 'federated ecosystem of research data infrastructures' will allow the scientific community to share and process publicly funded research results and data across borders and scientific domains.
- New Generation Metrics: New indicators must be developed to complement the conventional indicators for research quality and impact, so as to do justice to open science practices.
- Future of scholarly communication: all peer-reviewed scientific publications should be freely accessible, and the early sharing of different kinds of research outputs should be encouraged.
- Rewards: research career evaluation systems should fully acknowledge open science activities.
- Research integrity: all publicly funded research in the EU should adhere to commonly agreed standards of research integrity.
- Education and skills: all scientists in Europe should have the necessary skills and support to apply open science research routines and practices.
- Citizen science: the general public should be able to make significant contributions and be recognised as valid European science knowledge producers.

Open Science as Part of Research Culture

Positioning of the German Research Foundation

DFG

[Open science](#)[Principles for good scientific conduct](#)[Research data management](#) ...[Research support](#)

Open science

Open Science is a new approach to the scientific process that is based on cooperation, openness, and unrestricted access to research data, publications, and tools

The Open Science agenda stems from being able to access new types of digital technologies, tools, and infrastructures for collaborative research, as well as the need to access publicly supported research.

At DTU, researchers are focusing on this Open Science agenda in close collaboration with DTU Library, which has ensured a coherent infrastructure for the scientific process: Access to all necessary scientific literature through DTU Findit, the archiving and publishing of research data in [DTU Data](#), and the archiving of publications and associated Open Access versions at [DTU Orbit](#). Both DTU Orbit and DTU Data are globally and openly accessible systems that are contributing to the dissemination of scientific communication.

Based on this digital infrastructure, DTU has a unique opportunity to live up to the Open Science principles of openness in research. The ambition is for DTU to lead the way within the dissemination of FAIR data and to work in a targeted way with optimizing applications for Open Science output.

The objective in this area is to create even more transparency for DTU's research. The main infrastructure lines have been established, but a cultural change is required so that researchers think about the reusability of data in a broader sense than is currently the case. This change must, for example, be carried out in connection with addressing the practical applicability of the

-
1. Incentives & Culture
 2. Infrastructure
 3. Awareness/Knowledge/Skills

1. Incentives & Culture

2. Infrastructure

Text/Manuscript

Code/Models

Data

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USEFUL LINKS

Sign in to CLEAR

What's new

Support and training

Information about data security

<https://legal.thomsonreuters.com/en/products/clear-investigation-software>

Photo illustration: Sohee Cho/The Intercept, DWDS

BECOME
A MEMBER

LEXISNEXIS TO PROVIDE GIANT DATABASE OF PERSONAL INFORMATION TO ICE

The company signed a contract with an ICE division that plays a key role in deportations.

San Biddle

April 2 2021, 4:00 p.m.

THE POPULAR LEGAL RESEARCH and data brokerage firm LexisNexis signed a \$16.8 million contract to sell information to U.S. Immigration and

<https://theintercept.com/2021/04/02/ice-database-surveillance-lexisnexis/>

AUTHORITARIAN TECH

GODI KANUNHAZZE

Proposal to install spyware in university libraries to protect copyrights shocks academics

The hypothetical plan to combat digital piracy called for the use
of software to monitor those accessing academic material

BY GAUTAMA MEHTA 13 NOVEMBER, 2020 BRIEF

<https://www.codastory.com/authoritarian-tech/spyware-in-libraries/>

**Data tracking in research: aggregation and use or
sale of usage data by academic publishers**

A briefing paper of the Committee on Scientific Library Services and Information Systems of the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation)
28 October 2021

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Phone: +49 228 885-1 · Fax: +49 228 885-2777 · goemaster@dfg.de · www.dfg.de

Stop Tracking Science

The major academic publishers have made collection and trading of data about the research interests of individuals, groups and research institutions their new business model. Data about your scientific activities are collected in real time across the research workflow. The publishers take notes and sell the knowledge about you to third parties. This business model is in direct opposition to academic freedom. We have to stand up against these corporations!

3. Awareness/Knowledge/Skills

Open Educational Resources

Citizen Science

Open Licenses

SciComm

Accessibility

Diversity

Inclusion

Equity

Open Access

Post publication /
Open Peer-Review

Open Ideas

Open Grants

Pre-prints

Open Methodology

Open Lab Notebooks

Open collaborative writing

Open Data

Open Hardware

Open Models

Open Source

**Research
Cycle**

Idea

Study
design

Funding

Data
acquisition

Data
analysis

Manuscript

Peer review

Publication

MIND THE GAP

Key message:

To make science more open we need better incentives, solid infrastructure and training to equip more people with necessary skills.

A top-down view of a buffet table. The top half features several white square trays containing fresh green leafy salads, including spinach, arugula, and mixed greens. Below these are trays of sliced tomatoes, sliced cucumbers, and other vegetables. The bottom half of the image shows a large black tray divided into sections containing various cooked items: green beans, corn, red kidney beans, sliced tomatoes, green peas, shredded cheese, cubed chicken, and sliced onions. Two whole tomatoes are placed on the black tray as garnishes.

”Open Science is like a buffet:
take what you can and what benefits you now
– come back for more!”

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<https://www.biorxiv.org/>

re3data.org

REGISTRY OF RESEARCH DATA REPOSITORIES

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Transform to Open Science

Transform to Open Science (TOPS) is a \$40 million, 5-year mission, led by NASA's Science Mission Directorate's Open-Source Science initiative. Within the TOPS mission, NASA is designating 2023 as the Year Of Open Science, a community initiative to spark change and inspire open science...

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A large-scale COVID-19 Twitter chatter dataset for open scientific research - an international collaboration

[Banda, Juan M.](#); [Tekumalla, Ramya](#); [Wang, Guanyu](#); [Yu, Jingyuan](#); [Liu, Tuo](#); [Ding, Yuning](#); [Artemova, Katya](#); [Tutubalina, Elena](#); [Chowell, Gerardo](#)

Version 151 of the dataset. MAJOR CHANGE NOTE: The dataset files: full_dataset.tsv.gz and full_dataset_clean.tsv.gz have been split in 1 GB parts using the Linux utility called Split. So make sure to join the parts before unzipping. We had to make this change as we had huge issues uploading...

Uploaded on January 30, 2023

151 more version(s) exist for this record

[January 29, 2023 \(v0.5.9\)](#) [Software](#) [Open Access](#)[View](#)

Trixi.jl

[Schlottke-Lakemper, Michael](#); [Gassner, Gregor J.](#); [Ranocha, Hendrik](#); [Winters, Andrew R.](#); [Chan, Jesse](#)

<https://zenodo.org/>

Need help?

[Contact us](#)

Zenodo prioritizes all requested related to the COVID-19 outbreak.

We can help with:

- Uploading your research data, software, preprints, etc.
- One-on-one with Zenodo supporters.
- Quota increases beyond our default policy.
- Scripts for automated uploading of larger datasets.

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RESEARCH NOTE

REVISED An Open Science Peer Review Oath [version 2; peer review: 4 approved, 1 approved with reservations]

Jelena Aleksic¹, Adrian Alexa², Teresa K Attwood³, Neil Chue Hong⁹, Martin Dahlö⁴, Robert Davey ⁵, Holger Dinkel⁶, Konrad U Förstner⁷, Ivo Grigorov⁸, Jean-Karim Hériché⁶,

Leo Lahti ¹⁰, Dan MacLean¹¹, Michael L Markie¹², Jenny Molloy¹³, Maria Victoria Schneider⁵, Camille Scott¹⁴, Richard Smith-Unna¹⁵, Bruno Miguel Vieira¹⁶, as part of the AIBio: Open Science & Reproducibility Best Practice Workshop

Author details

This article is included in the [Research on Research, Policy & Culture](#) gateway.

Abstract

One of the foundations of the scientific method is to be able to reproduce experiments and corroborate the results of research that has been done before. However, with the increasing complexities of new technologies and techniques, coupled with the specialisation of

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		↑	↑	↑		↑
Version 1	12 Nov 14	? read	? read	? read	✓ read	? read

- Vitaly Citovsky**, University of New York at Stony Brook, Stony Brook, USA
- Christopher D Chambers**, Cardiff University, Cardiff, UK

DORA

(Declaration on Research Assessment)

LEIDEN MANIFESTO FOR RESEARCH METRICS

<https://sfdora.org/> / <http://www.leidenmanifesto.org/>

Résumé for Researchers

Opening up conversations about researcher evaluation

Résumé for Researchers has been created to support the evaluation of individuals' varied contributions to research. Find out more about the background to the tool [in our blog](#).

Sustained excellence in research requires a range of contributions

By creating a working environment that is both challenging and supportive, researchers help improve the flow of ideas, encourage talent to join their organisations and nurture future generations of researchers. To make the decisions concerning the people that create such an environment, decision-makers need to be able to assess the previous contributions made by individuals.

Over the years, the research community has developed ways of assessing contributions to the development of new ideas often by focusing on individuals' portfolios of outputs and the impact of their work. However, a researcher's overall contribution to research goes beyond their easily attributable outputs and impact. Too narrowly focused performance indicators can make it harder to see, reward or nurture the full range of contributions that are necessary to create the environments that enable excellence and steward it for the future. To recognise these wider contributions, the Society aims to prompt conversations on the evaluation of researchers.

Showing the full range of an individual's contributions to excellent research

To prompt such conversations the Society has developed Résumé for Researchers, which is intended to help researchers to share their varied contributions to research in a consistent way and across a wide range of circumstances.

Résumé for Researchers is not designed to replace more granular information where needed. The strength of the tool lies in its ability to provide a concise overview of an individual. It draws from other established and internationally recognised biosketches, assessment matrices and application forms, as well as having the Society's own evaluation methodology at its heart.

<https://royalsociety.org/topics-policy/projects/research-culture/tools-for-support/resume-for-researchers/>

Downloads

[Résumé for Researchers suggested template](#)

PDF, 114.5KB

[← Tools to support and steward research culture](#)

**EUROPEAN OPEN
SCIENCE CLOUD**

<https://eosc-portal.eu/>

<https://www.nfdi.de/>

NFDI4
MICROBIOTA

<https://nfdi4microbiota.de/>

Key message:

Open Science needs both – joint actions of research communities and individual practice. Every step counts.

PUSH TO
RESET THE
WORLD

-
- The background of the slide is a close-up photograph of a blue-painted metal surface, possibly a door or a cabinet. The paint is peeling and chipped away in several places, revealing a rusty, brown metal underneath. A large, rectangular, gold-colored padlock is attached to the metal. The padlock has the word "STERLING" and a logo of a bird with spread wings embossed on its front. The overall scene suggests a state of decay or a barrier that needs to be broken down.
- Openness, transparency, reproducibility are core values of science.
 - To make science more open we need better incentives, solid infrastructure and training to equip more people with necessary skills.
 - Open Science needs both – joint actions of research communities and individual practice. Every step counts.

Thank you for your attention. What are your questions?

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